

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH ANTHROPNYMS

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the historical development of anthroponyms, which was evaluating during many centuries. English proper names have a long history of development and functionalizing. What is more, national features of proper names find their reflection in the anthroponomical formula. Proper names, functionalizing at the current stage in English language, were created and borrowed from various sources and entered the system of proper by names gradually.

English anthroponomical system, as English language, was influenced by different cultures and languages from early periods of its formation. Indo-European tribes as Belgians, Britons, Celts and others settled in British islands in the eight century BC and brought their own system of proper names, which had Indo-European origin and accordingly was similar to the Slavic, Greek and other systems of naming. For instance, more names of Celt origin contained one-component, two-component and derivational proper names. However, the Celtic era left minor traces of modern nominal English language system. And the reason for this was historical fact that Jutes, Saxons and Angles pushed the Celts to the North and West of the islands, destroying or assimilating the remaining part of inhabitants, they brought own system of anthroponyms. Thus, more anthroponyms of the Celts origin disappeared or anglicized, acquired a form similar to English proper names. Anthroponyms formula in this system involved only first name which was sometimes followed by a patronymic or toponymic nickname. The reason for this was the formation of their community and a big variety of anthroponyms system. In this period two-component names gradually replaced one-

component names, what is more, at the end of XIII century they had not almost found in the nomenclature of English proper names.

Further Britain was captured by the Romans (in 43 AD) and remained as a part of Rome Empire for several centuries. During that time such a famous name as Julianus, Claudius, Sergius appeared.

Another significant historical event which affected English folk and its language was the Scandinavian conquest (VIII century). The ancient Scandinavians were people of German origin, their language belonged to the Germanic group and Old Norse anthroponyms were close to old English ones. Thus, the Scandinavian conquest did not influence too much on the general English system of proper names. In modern English anthroponymy there are a number of proper names related to the ancient Scandinavians. They are not very popular among today's society, however, are excited and are used. Thus, the period of V-XI centuries in the history of development of English anthroponyms system is characterized by radical changes influenced by linguistic and extra-linguistic factors.

Further another vital important and new period of the evaluating in English linguo-community was coming and it was the Norman conquest. The Normans had conquered Britain and brought their own language, culture and names. Norman anthroponyms became very popular among the upper classes and urban residents very fast, pushing aside the old English anthroponyms. The Normans had Scandinavian origin, they were Germans and had not only borrowed proper names but also ancient Germanic proper names in their anthroponyms system, which were spread in the Anglo-Saxon variation among English people. Before the Norman conquest the ancient English had opportunity to create new names changing or connecting components from different names, however, the Norman anthroponyms system was different. Names were traditionally given from generation to generation, children were named after relatives or close friends. Names with old English origin were almost disappeared after the Normans. The Norman conquest also brought to the acceleration of the transition of nicknames into surnames.

It is also necessary to note that the Christian religion influenced enormously on the formation and development of English proper names. The process of conversion to the Christian religion began in the seventh century in England. The power of the church became so strong, that the church could demand that believers name their children with names of canonized saints. The names of spiritual fathers were wide spread in that period. In the sixteenth century after the establishment of the Lutheran and Anglican churches, naming a newborn with any name chosen by godparents was allowed. By the middle of the century, a name given at baptism was officially registered and recorded in documents. However, in this period the owner could have many nicknames and surnames, which were not registered officially. Surnames transmitted through father's line were officially established in 1730. In this period English anthroponymy was replenished with proper names of the biblical origin.

Next event which influenced on English anthroponymy was the socio-political movement-Reformation, that was developing in the Western and Central Europe in the sixteenth century. England was also gripped by this movement. The reformation brought the development of a new variation of Christianity- Protestantism and Lutheranism. The reformation brought significant changes to the system of proper names of the English. The reformers demanded not

only to abandon Catholic customs and rituals, but also personal names, which the Catholic Church recommended to its followers. The Reformation of the Church demanded a recourse to biblical names. Personal names of the church calendar, which supplanted original English names, were the most popular in that period.

In the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries the most radical supporters of the church reformation- Puritans appeared in England. Peculiarities of their views were reflected in the process of creating names of English people. They brought a number of novelties to anthroponymy of the English. They believed that the English Church was godless and the names it recommended were disgraceful. Thus, Puritans recommended Latinized and rare biblical names, which sounded curiously. Such strange and uncharacteristic for English language names have not been used for a long time and disappeared by the nineteenth century.

In 1660 after the English bourgeois revolution the basic registered fund contained Old English, Norman, biblical, saint's names, names created after surnames and Puritan names. Not only English language, but also the system of English proper names represented multilingual mixing. People chose names for their children taking into consideration the fashion for certain proper names. Giving names became the matter of personal taste and desire. Additionally, double proper names, which were written separately but considered as single, were popular in female anthroponymy in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries (e.g. *Amelia Rose, Autumn-Rose, Celia-Anne, Ada-Lucy*).

In the XIX-XX centuries is the period of further widening of English anthroponymy. Revived their former popularity, continue to exist Old English names, biblical and saint's names, derived names from surnames were widespread, the usage of diminutive names as full ones was quite popular. Inheritance of proper names from one generation to another became a tradition in English community. At that time children were named after monarchs, as well as fiction influenced on English anthroponym. A big number of literature characters were quite popular, so their names were given to children by many generations. Cinematography, music, television, fashion and pop-culture also affect the English system of proper names, people try to give their children unique and original names, sometimes changing the orthographical variation of popular name.

The XX-XXI centuries characterize as the period of globalization, development of communication system, mutual influence and interconnection of different cultures. A frequent usage of short names, which are officially registered, observed, ethical, gender and national features in the structure of proper names doesn't matter. The most significant factor in choosing names for native speakers in this period is the desire to individualize personality through original and expressive names.

In conclusion, English anthroponymy had a long way of development, currently they represent the result of evaluation of countries, languages, religious and trends in names. The evaluation of the system of proper names is closely connected with the historical development of society and influence of extralinguistic factors.

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